

NEOVASCULOSTOP

PARADIGM SHIFT IN NEOVASCULARIZATION TREATMENT

Acronym:

NeoVasculoStop

Project Title:

Natural Intraocular Photoactivation of Compounds to Fight Retinopathies

Grant Agreement No:

101047120

Call:

HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01

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Deliverable 1.1

Deliverable 1.1	Project Management Handbook
Associated WP	WP1 – Project management
Associated Task(s)	Task 1.1 General management
Due Date	30/04/2022
Date Delivered	30/04/2022
Prepared by	LC
Partners involved	EXPERIM
Authors	Ákos Murányi (LC), Nagyová Katarína (LC), Péter Mogyorósi (LC), Jenni Hakkarainen (EXPERIM)
Deliverable Version	1.0
Dissemination Level	PU

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Purpose

The purpose of this Project Management Guide is to provide a detailed description of the project structure and its delivery methods and controls to realise the project's defined objectives. The document includes definitions about how the project is going to be executed, monitored and controlled and it intends to be a working tool to provide context and guidelines to the partners for the successful conduct of the project. Accordingly, it will be maintained throughout the life of the project as a living document, subject to formal change control.

The Project Management Guide provides details about the organisation of the project, specifically:

- Project Scope overview
- Management structure and procedures
- Deliverables
- Reporting Periods
- Risk Management overview

Other project administrative documents that are relevant are:

- Grant Agreement (GA)
- Consortium Agreement (CA)

Both documents will be available on the Project management tool. In the event of a legal dispute, the CA and GA will form the basis for the resolution of the dispute since these are signed by the partners' authorised representatives (note: GA will take preference over the CA). The GA is fixed at the project start and can only be amended by means of formal EC procedures.

Project Scope

List of Participants

Number	Role	Short Name	Legal Name	Country	PIC
1	COO	EXPERIM	EXPERIMENTICA OY	FI	937022038
1.1	AE	EX- PERIM_UAB	EXPERIMENTICA UAB	LT	904952383
2	BEN	VICHEM	VICHEM CHEMIE KUTATO KORLATOLT FELELOSSEGU TARSASAG	HU	998482111
3	BEN	SE	SEMMELWEIS EGYETEM	HU	999860675
4	BEN	NEOW	NEOX S.R.O	CZ	888419703
5	BEN	LC	LASER CONSULT MUSZAKI- TUDOMANYOS ES GAZDASAGI TANACSADO KORLATOLT FELELOS- SEGU TARSASAG	HU	944016126

Main Objectives

The specific objectives of the project are laid down in a way that, at the project closure, one lead molecule (a modified inhibitor), one follow-up molecule, furthermore all the results and the documentation be available to start a human phase I clinical trial. The steps leading to these objectives can be summarized as follows:

- We will synthesize modified VEGFR inhibitors based on in silico work: vorolanib and other parent compounds will be modified at different positions. Expected result: activatable molecules, that can permanently inhibit VEGF signaling as assessed first in in vitro biochemical VEGFR kinase assays and then in cell culture experiments (measurable outcome: extent (%) of binding, extent (%) of inhibition, its permanent nature upon irradiation).
- We will test the best candidate molecules on cultured human retinal microvascular endothelial cells (HRMEC) to verify their potential to block neovascularization. Measurable outcome: the percent of reduction of (i) tube formation on matrigel and (ii) migration in Boyden-chamber.
- We will produce at least one further molecule derived from a different VEGFR inhibitor via a specific chemical modification.
- Using healthy experimental animals (rats and mice) we will test the enrichment of the compounds in the retina by exposure to natural light and upon artificial irradiation. Measurable outcome is (i) the amount of the compound in the retina and (ii) the ratio of the retinally targeted and circulating amount of the compound, as measured by mass spectrometry analysis of blood samples and of retinal tissue.
- Using preclinical animal models we will test the efficiency of the compounds in the (i) rat streptozotocin - induced DR, (ii) mouse laser-induced choroidal neovascularization as a model of AMD, and (iii) in the rabbit model of retinal neovascularization induced by intravitreal administration of DL-2-aminoadipic acid (DL-AAA). Several parameters are to be tested (see „Implementation” section).
- To prove the absence of toxicity and verify the tolerability of the modified compounds, we will test that in post mortem human retinae and will run complete GLP-conform preclinical studies.
- We will produce all the documents required for the human phase I clinical trial based on the experiments above.

Our envisioned strategy uses light in a fundamentally different manner than laser is used in photodynamic therapy to treat AMD or in photocoagulation therapy to treat DR. Therefore our project constitutes a high risk/high gain research approach given that no experiments have yet been performed to verify our core concept. The in vivo biodistribution experiment with modified compounds is the first test that can reliably identify such potency. Therefore, as indicated in the risk management table, upon suboptimal retinal targeting by natural light, artificial light of increasing intensity and defined wavelength will be tested in experimental animals. Simultaneously, input will be asked from the medical experts within the consortium

(NEOX) to re-design the follow-up projects, including the phase II clinical trial, to include a wearable light source that is to be manufactured by a further partner company. Of note, even if a wearable light source is essential in addition to the oral administration of our drug, the new treatment is still noninvasive and superior to the one available at present.

No gender dimension is taken into account in the project given that the envisioned treatment of the targeted disease conditions is the same for any and all genders.

Management Structure and Procedures

Management Structure

The governance structure of the NeoVasculoStop project has been conceived to ensure a fair and transparent project management and to grant partners an adequate level of representation and decision making. All partners assume full technical and financial responsibility for the management of the project. The organization structure will be composed by different bodies represented in *1. Figure*. The management structure has been organized taking into account the size of the consortium and the complexity of the project and highlighting the importance of industrial application of the project results.

Project Management Roles

- **Project Officer (PO)**
- **Project Coordinator (PC) - EXPERIM**

Maintaining contact between the consortium and the EC, Coordination with and Reporting to the EC (tracking and reporting progress), Coordination and careful monitoring of the activities of the project (with the assistance of a project management tool, will be set up at M3), Administrative management of the project, checking and submitting deliverables, Financial administration of the project, distribute the payments received from the granting authority to the other beneficiaries without unjustified delay, Overseeing the different managerial positions, Ensuring all partners adhere to the contractual obligations of the Grant Agreement, Ensuring compliance with the Consortium Agreement, Overseeing the promotion of gender equality in the project

- **Project manager - LC**

Responsible for intra-project communication, organization and documentation of the general project meetings, organization of the executive board and the general assembly and their meetings, the Project Management Handbook, a continuous risk monitoring and assessment.

- **General Assembly**

The Ultimate decision-making body of the consortium shall consist of one representative of each Party.

- **Executive Board**

Executive Board as the supervisory body for the execution of the Project which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly. The Executive Board shall consist of the Coordinator and the Parties appointed by the General Assembly.

1. Figure

Management Procedures

Partners responsibility:

- Effective economic management and conduct of the operational work in accordance with the program guidelines and ethical and legal standards.
- Complying with the general terms and conditions governing grants and any terms and conditions specific to each grant or granting programme established by the European Commission.
- Managing and supervising operational personnel.
- Meeting reporting requirements specific to Horizon Europe and the specificity of the call.
- Acknowledging, whenever possible, the Coordinator's financial support for the operational work.

Internal communication flow

There must be effective interaction between activities and tasks, and, in order to ensure collaboration, fulfilment of goals and good general functioning of the consortium, there will be regular meetings including representatives from WP Leaders. This will guarantee the synchronisation of all the tasks, define control procedures to follow the evolution of work, solve potential conflicts between partners, define dissemination policies for results and plan the presentation of common communications.

Teleconferences, email, and web exchange will be used as the primary forms of communication and exchange of documents among the partners.

The Consortium will hold in-person meetings to disseminate technical progress through a presentation of results and peer review, co-ordinate and cohere project planning. Consensus in decision-making is highly desirable, both for quality assurance and to ensure that the goals and interests of the partners are respected.

Monitoring and progress reporting

Each partner and WP leader will report project progress to the Project Coordinator on a regular basis. This will cover technical progress, results, deliverables and compliance with the WP schedule. The monitoring of the identified risks should be reported to the Project Manager and updated in the relevant online risk table.

Knowledge management

Knowledge management deals with assessing the results of the NeoVasculoStop project for novelty, patentability and freedom to operate in order the most appropriate IPR strategy can be defined. The joint ownership and the access to knowledge/results of the NeoVasculoStop project are already specified within the CA and GA. Additional knowledge management measures will be implemented if necessary.

Conflict resolution

Conflicts will be solved at the lowest level possible, and preferably amicably. If an agreement cannot be reached at a task or WP level, then the Project Coordinator will mediate. If that is

not satisfactory, then the General Assembly will make a decision and, if necessary, will ask for the authorization of the EC.

Dissemination and Communication

A detailed dissemination & communication guideline will be created by the Project Manager keeping in mind the best practices and guidelines of the EU. The PM will monitor that these guidelines are followed by all partners.

Data management

The data management policy will be created in which the rules for data creation, storage and use will be described, keeping in mind the EU ethical and data management guidelines. These rules will apply for the duration of the project and beyond. This policy will be included and constantly updated in the Data Management Plan deliverable.

Progress Monitoring

The main mechanisms that will be used for progress monitoring are:

- Progress report: the PC will collect progress reports from each WP Leader and financial reports from each participant, every reporting period. These reports will be the main tool for internal monitoring and after revision and approval, they will be shared among the consortium via e-mail. In addition to the research advance, reports should also include information on dissemination, communication and outreach actions.
- Review meetings: The aim of the review meeting is to inform the Project officer about the progress of the project. During the lifetime of the NeoVasculoStop project there will be three review meetings, held on M14, M32, M49 in Brussels attended by at least one representative of each participant. Technical/scientific review meeting documents will be prepared as a WP8 deliverable in M13, M31, M48 which will be sent in advance to the Project officer and will serve as the basis of the review meeting.
- General meetings: the Consortium will hold at least one meeting every year.
 - Kick-off meeting, May 12-13, 2022, Budapest, Hungary
 - The final schedule of the meetings will be finalized on and after the Kick-off meeting.
- Deliverables: deliverables and milestones will be of paramount importance for the project monitoring and information sharing with the EC. The list of deliverables and the procedure to prepare them are described in the following point of this document.
- Reporting: the project is divided into three periods (M12, M30 and M48). After each period, formal reports must be completed and progress meetings with EC representatives arranged.
- Informative e-mails: the PC will circulate informative e-mails through the WP Leaders to every or all the partners depending on the issues.

- Formal Amendments: if changes in budget, person-month distribution, etc. are needed, approved changes require amendments to the GA, the PC will be in charge of requesting them to the EC (with supporting documents).

Deliverables

Schedulement of the Deliverables:

Responsibility of partners:

WP leader and task leader: responsible for the content and quality of the deliverable while keeping the deadlines.

Coordinator: responsible for tracking the progress of deliverables and for the timeliness of their submission.

Submission procedure:

Deadline minus 5 weeks: 1st draft (containing at least: a full table of contents, partners responsible for the deliverable, min. 60% of content) sent to partners.

Deadline minus 4 weeks: feedback on 1st draft is sent back.

Deadline minus 3 weeks: final draft is sent to the coordinator, who circulates it to all partners for feedback.

Deadline minus 2 weeks: all feedback is sent back.

Deadline minus 1 weeks: final version is sent to the coordinator for submission.

2. Figure

Clearance Procedure (Deliverable Documents)

The general procedure to be followed for reporting deliverables is:

- PC sends an email to all WP leaders with deliverables due in the following period about the deadlines / due dates for the draft and final version of the deliverables
- The WP Leader assigns the partners responsible for drafting the deliverable according to the specific template (document templates will be available in the intranet website), including a control system (responsible, version, reviewers and approval).
- Once the draft has been circulated, revised and approved by the Work package participants, the WP Leader sends it to the PC (with enough time for revision).
- The PC will revise the document and suggest modifications. This will be an iterative process until the required quality standards are met.
- The PC will be responsible for submitting the final version of the deliverable, in due time, through the Participant Portal using the SyGMA system for continuous reporting.
- If one or more of the Parties is late in submission of any project deliverable, PC may nevertheless submit the other Parties project deliverables and all other documents required by the GA to the Funding Authority in time.

Deliverables must be completed by the due date. In the case that any justified issue prevents meeting the deadline, the PC should be informed as soon as possible and must contact the PO to find a possible solution (amendment, delivery of a draft instead of a final document, etc.).

Reporting Periods

At the end of each reporting period the PC must submit a full report to the EC (through the Participant Portal). The full reports consist in two parts: Financial Report & Technical Report.

Technical Report

Part A: tables to be filled in the management system (SyGMA) with information about deliverables, milestones, publications, etc. The PC will update the needed tables.

Part B: report containing an overview of the project's advance and the exploitation/dissemination of the results. The report must follow a specific template provided by the EC. The PC will be in charge of disposing the required template so the involved partners can use it, and of ensuring compliance and on-time delivery. The report will be based on the internal progress report, and the *general procedure for reporting deliverables* will be followed during its preparation.

Financial Management and Reporting

The Financial Report consists of:

- Detailed individual financial statement for each beneficiary
- Explanation of the use of resources

Each partner must prepare its financial report, each of them being the only one responsible for its content. The PC will check the consistency of the financial reports with the technical one and submit the full report.

Internal Financial and Progress Reports

To facilitate budget management, the PC will ask for internal financial reports every reporting period containing:

- Expenses incurred during the previous period
- Effort in each WP (person month used)
- Deviations occurred
- Future deviations envisaged (if any)
- Any changes in the budget will be discussed during the Consortium meetings.

The internal financial report should be prepared by each partner, reporting the advances of the project as well as the progress or completion of the tasks and subtasks in each given period. It is important to keep in mind that these will be used as the basis for the full report submitted by the PC to the EC at the end of the reporting period.

Audits

A Certificate on Financial Statements (CFS) per institution is needed if the total direct costs for that institution are higher than 430,000€.